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Modeling the groundwater flow of a coastal Mediterranean region aquifer under climate change scenarios.

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Short abstract. Climate change is adding pressure to the coastal areas and their aquifers. Numerical tools are widely used for modeling and monitoring the aquifers’ condition considering climate change scenarios. This work is referred to the Malia area in Crete, Greece. The tool that was used in this work is FEFLOW software. Climate change scenarios were used to assess potential effect on groundwater budget confirming that there will be a depression in the groundwater level. The Regional Climate Models that were used are based on 2 Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5).

Keywords. Coastal Aquifer, FEFLOW, Malia area.

Introduction

The location of the Mediterranean region can lead to crucial changes. The increase of greenhouse gases makes the Mediterranean region particularly vulnerable to climate change (1). In this work we are referred to an area on the island of Crete in Greece. Specifically, for the region of Malia, Crete a study was performed about the projections of Regional Climate Models (RCMs) regarding the mean temperature and precipitation which showed a negative trend during the period 2010-2040 (2). For the period 2040-2098, the situation appears to be worse with a greater decrease in the average precipitation and also an increase in temperature (3). Because of the increasing demands for water and the decrease of precipitation this work aims to assess the impact of the future climatic scenarios on the groundwater resources.

This work presents the simulation of the Malia aquifer system with the use of the numerical simulator FEFLOW which is an advanced Finite Element subsurface FLOW and transport modelling system (4).

The simulations are based on data in the study area for the period 2000-2012. The data that are used are obtained either from the literature or from field measurements that are available on different databases.

The climate scenarios that were used in this work were produced in collaboration with the University of Parma. The climate projections were produced by 17 RCMs based on two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs 4.5 and 8.5). The period 1976-2005 consists of the historical data and the period 2006-2098 is the scenario period.

Material and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area is located about 40 km east of the city of Heraklion, Crete and its characterized by a mountainous area the Selena Mountains (5). The area is used for agriculture. The main cultivation of the lower altitude areas is potatoes and the areas that are located at higher altitudes are olives and vineyards (6). In the Mediterranean, the precipitation becomes less and more erratic year by year. This causes reduced groundwater recharge therefore lower groundwater levels. Also, without protecting the aquifers the drinking water quality is deteriorated because of the salinization and waterborne environmental risks (7). In Greece, the quality of the groundwater declined after the dry period of 1980 – 1990 when the entire country was affected (8). The island of Crete has a typical eastern Mediterranean climate which means that is a semi-arid region with high seasonal precipitation patterns (9). 40% of the annual precipitation occurs during the winter months and during summer the precipitation is negligible (10). The soil of the study area consists of 2 different soils Calcaric Regosol and Calcaric Leptosol. Calcaric Regosol is characterized by weak cohesion, high infiltrability, and low water retention ability (11).

2.2. Geology

The mountainous area is composed of the series Phyllites – Quartzites and the series of Tripolis. The Phyllitic – Quartzitic series acts as the impermeable substrate of the region (13). The Phyllite – Quartzite series consists of a) a variety of greenish schists, mainly chloritic-sericitic ones, more or less graphitic schists that usually intercalate with thin grey Quartzitic layers, b) Quartzite – schist alternations, c) schist – thin-bedded marble alternation and d) blonde – yellowish to red – yellowish schists containing sparse Quartzitic layers. The Tripolis zone is represented by a) Tyros beds, b) Carbonate series and c) the flysch (14). The Neogene units layover Tripolis carbonated rocks and they consist of bioclastic, partly breccious, or conglomeratic limestones and reefal limestones. At the northern part of the area, the Pleistocene – Holocene surficial sediments cover the older geological formations. The Pleistocene – Holocene sediments consist of alluvial, marine terrace deposits, talus cones, and scree (6).

2.3. Model development

The study area has a width of about 17.3 km and a length of about 15.3 km. The discretization of the unconfined aquifer was applied using a triangular finite element mesh which consists of 185665 nodes and 290912 elements. There are 4 layers and each one of them has 72728 and 5 slices with 37133 nodes for each slice. The depth of the model is 83 m below the sea level. The information for the elevation of the area was provided by Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and the file that was imported to the FEFLOW model was prepared in ArcGIS. The aquifer thickness was divided in four layers according to hydrogeological information. At the southern part of the aquifer, the maximum surface elevation is approximately 1420 m, and in the northern part the elevation is at sea level. The thickness of the first layer depends on the variability of surface elevation at each point. The data for the hydraulic conductivity were obtained from the database of the Decentralized Administration of Crete. The values of hydraulic conductivity along the z'z axis were set at 10% of the x'x and y'y axis

according to literature. Rainfall information were considered from 2 local rainfall stations. These stations are located at different elevations one is in the South part (elevation 820 m asl) and the other one in the East part (elevation 265 m asl) of the study area. The rainfall data are daily time series for the period 01/2000- 12/2012.

In the area of Malia, there are 11 observation wells. The reference data period is for the years 2000-2012. Measurements were conducted irregularly so the observation period for each well varies.

The data of 407 pumping wells that are distributed in the entire study area is used considering their pumping rates. Due to the large number of pumping wells, they were clustered to groups of 20. The grouping was implemented using the ArcGIS by taking into consideration the X, Y coordinates and the pumping rate. Then for it's of the groups the median center was found. The 20 new wells consider the information of every single well that belongs to each group. The new pumping rate is the sum of the pumping rates of the wells that constitute every group.

The model also requires the assignment of boundary conditions for the simulation of the hydraulic head. Then the model compares its results with the observed field data (15). For the model of the Malia area, a first-type flow boundary condition was used along the coastline, where the hydraulic head was set at 0 m. At the South of the study area, a second-type flow boundary condition was used. The boundary condition was generated by dividing the daily rainfall rate by the daily average rainfall of the entire period 2000-2012. Then the quotient is multiplied with a boundary condition coefficient (estimated by the model) and was found by applying trial and error.

For the climatic models' assessment on the aquifer expected impact, the same principle as in the original model was used. The data for the climate models considered rainfall variability with a range up to the year 2098. The rainfall data were used as time series and were divided in two periods. The boundary conditions at the South of the study area were similarly defined to the original model and a First-type flow boundary conditions remained on the coastline.

Results and discussion

Figure 1. Comparison of the hydraulic head of RCP 4.5 with RCP 8.5

As it appears in Figure 1 there is a comparison of the hydraulic head at the 11 observation wells. On the left the results of the climate scenario RCP4.5 are presented and on the right those for the RCP 8.5. First, the discussion is focused on the observation well that is located in the south of the study area. For that specific well the hydraulic head variations can be observed with the naked eye. The RCP 4.5 results show a small increase in the hydraulic head until the year 2024 with a hydraulic head value almost 120 meters above sea level. After the year 2024 there is a decrease in the hydraulic head until the end of the simulation, year 2098, and the water table is shaped to 80 meters above sea level. The RCP 8.5 results on the other hand, presents from the beginning of the simulation a decrease in the hydraulic head until the year 2040 where the water table is at almost 80 meters above sea level. Then there is a small increase for a few years which is followed by a decrease, with the hydraulic head to remain constantly below 80 meters. The same behaviour is observed for the other wells with lower

hydraulic heads but the decrease in meters is smaller and it is difficult to appear on the graph. The climate scenario data were used on the existing calibrated model. The calibration of the flow was based on the hydraulic heads. The results of the original groundwater flow model model show an average validation error of less than 10% signifying that the model settings and results are reliable.

Conclusions

This study emphasizes the fact that climate change can cause significant changes in coastal aquifers in the Mediterranean region. The present study using numerical modelling technique yields results that are useful to monitor and model the groundwater level variability. The results show that the expected climate change effects will cause a significant decrease in the groundwater level at the short term and on the long-term. Variations are easier to be observed in wells with high hydraulic heads. Also, at wells of lower heads, there is proportionally the same decrease. The outcome of this work should emerge the local authorities to take the appropriate measures to control the over pumping of the aquifer and to adopt an innovative governance and policy for the water resources management of the basin.

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